

THE PREFERENTIAL ACYLATION OF β -HYDROXYL GROUP IN 3-NITROALIZARIN

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An additional experimental evidence has been put forth in support of the preferential acylation of β -hydroxy group in the alizarin molecule.

It has been reported by Dimroth, Friedman and Kammerer (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 481) that it is possible to acylate the β -hydroxyl group without affecting the α one, by using moderate conditions of experiment. It is a question of relative rates; the acetylation of the α -hydroxyl group is more sluggish than that in β position. It is also known that the OH group in α -position cannot be readily alkylated by the usual alkylating procedures. The methylation of the α -OH group can be effected only by heating the dry K-salt with dimethyl sulphate. Methylation of the α -OH group is known to be greatly facilitated by first reducing the anthraquinone system and then methylating the "leuco" compound by the normal methods.

The observed inactivity of the α -OH group may be due to chelation, H of OH sharing the electron pair of the O of CO group :

The observed increased activity of the leuco derivative (in the leuco, CO is changed to -C-OH and no chelation is possible) greatly supports such an assumption.

We have been able to put forward additional evidence that a β -hydroxy group is preferentially acylated under moderate conditions of working. Thus, we have acylated (acetylated and benzoylated) 3-nitroalizarin in pyridine at 100°, using equimolar quantities of the acyl chloride and the nitroalizarin. The acyl derivative formed in either case was found to be the 2-acyl-3-nitroalizarin. This has been established in the following way :—

1. The analytical results show that the compounds obtained on acylation are mono-acyl derivatives.

2. The mono-acyl derivative is reduced with zinc dust and 50% acetic acid to the corresponding amine; the latter is then refluxed with P₂O₅ in toluene when an oxazole derivative is formed which is further acylated (acetylated and benzoylated) to give a known oxazole derivative.

The acetyl compound shows no depression of m.p. when mixed with a small quantity of the compound obtained from 1 : 2-diacetyl-3-aminoalizarin by refluxing with P_2O_5 in toluene.

Similarly, the final product with monobenzoyl-3-nitroalizarin would be

which has been found to be the actual case. It is identical with the compound obtained by refluxing of the 1 : 2-dibenzoyl-3-aminoalizarin with P_2O_5 in toluene.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 2-Acetyl-3-nitroalizarin (I).—3-Nitroalizarin (5 g.) was dissolved in warm pyridine (50 ml.) kept in a round-bottomed flask (250 ml. capacity) and fitted with a condenser. To this solution acetyl chloride (1.5 ml., slightly more than equimolar quantity) was added. The reaction was allowed to proceed on a water-bath at 100° for 8 hours, and then allowed to stand for 24 hours. No derivative crystallised out. However, on pouring the reaction mixture into 200 ml. of water, the acetyl derivative separated out. It was collected at the pump, washed with water several times and dried. It was finally crystallised from benzene in orange needles, m.p. 231° , yield 83%. (Found: C, 59.11; H, 3.03; N, 4.12. $C_{16}H_9O_7N$ requires C, 58.71 H, 2.76; N, 4.28 per cent).

Reduction of (I) to 2-Acetyl-3-aminoalizarin.—The compound (I, 5 g.) was dissolved in 50% acetic acid (60 ml.) kept in a conical flask. To the warm solution zinc dust (3 g.) was added (a little quantity at a time) with vigorous shaking of the mixture. The contents of the flask became gradually deep red. The reaction flask was then placed in a water-bath at 50° for one hour, and the warm solution quickly filtered. The filtrate was diluted with water when the amino compound separated out. It was collected, washed free from acid with water, dried and finally crystallised from alcohol in red needles, m.p. 217°.

Oxazole Ring Formation.—2-Acetyl-3-aminoalizarin (3 g.) and P_2O_5 (1 g.) were added to dry toluene (40 ml.) and the reaction mixture boiled under reflux for 3 hours. It was then allowed to cool when the oxazole derivative separated out. It was collected at the pump, washed free from toluene with ether and then with water from the phosphorus compounds and finally dried, when yellowish brown needles melting at 236° were obtained in 65% yield. (Found C, 68.30; H, 3.52; N, 4.88. $C_{16}H_9O_4N$ requires C, 68.81; H, 3.22; N, 5.01 per cent). The compound is soluble in Na_2CO_3 and NaOH solutions in the cold giving violet solutions. It dissolves in concentrated H_2SO_4 with orange colour.

On acetylation by the usual procedure, a product was formed which on crystallisation from benzene was identical with the oxazole obtained from 1:2-diacetyl-3-aminoalizarin, by refluxing with P_2O_5 in toluene.

Preparation of Oxazole from 1:2-Diacetyl-3-nitroalizarin: (a). Preparation of 1:2-Diacetyl-3-nitroalizarin.—To 3-nitroalizarin (10 g.), dissolved in hot nitrobenzene (50 ml.), a large excess of acetyl chloride (12 ml.) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed on a sand-bath for 6 hours. On cooling, the diacetyl derivative crystallised out. It was collected at the pump and washed free from nitrobenzene with petrol as yellow needles, m.p. 213°, yield 80%.

(b). *Reduction of 1:2-Diacetyl-3-nitroalizarin* was carried out by using the same procedure as in the case of 2-acetyl-3-nitroalizarin, described above. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. at 240°.

(c). *Oxazole formation* was carried out in the same way as described above in the case of 2-acetyl-3-aminoalizarin. The product formed light brown needles, m.p. 268°, yield 68%. (Found: C, 67.80; H, 3.60; N, 4.42. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 67.29; H, 3.42; N, 4.36 per cent).

Preparation of 2-Benzoyl-3-nitroalizarin.—The method employed is essentially the same as in the acetylation; benzoyl chloride (28 ml.) was used in place of 1.5 ml. of acetyl chloride. The product on crystallisation from nitrobenzene formed orange coloured needles, m.p. 302°, yield 79%.

Reduction of 2-Benzoyl-3-nitroalizarin.—The nitro compound was reduced with zinc dust and acetic acid as in the case of the corresponding acetyl derivative. On crystallisation from alcohol it formed deep orange needles, m.p. 254°.

Oxazole formation was effected in the same way as that used in the case of the corresponding 2-acetyl-3-aminoalizarin. The compound was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 278°, yield 70%.

It dissolves in sodium carbonate and caustic alkali and gives a violet solution. With concentrated H_2SO_4 , it gives an orange coloured solution. (Found: C, 74.31; H, 3.36; N, 4.29. $C_{21}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 73.90; H, 3.32; N, 4.10 per cent). On benzoylation by the usual procedure, a product was formed which on crystallisation from benzene was found to be identical with the oxazole obtained from 1:2-dibenzoyl-3-aminoalizarin by refluxing with P_2O_5 in toluene.

Preparation of Oxazole from 1:2-Dibenzoyl-3-nitroalizarin: (a). Preparation of 1:2-Benzoyl-3-nitroalizarin.—This was obtained by the same procedure as in the preparation of the diacetyl derivative using 20 ml. (excess) of benzoyl chloride in place of acetyl chloride. The product was freed from traces of benzoic acid by repeated washing with water, m.p. 276–78°, yield 85%.

(b). *Reduction of 1:2-Benzoyl-3-nitroalizarin.*—Procedure was the same as under the corresponding 1:2-diacetyl derivative. The product on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave yellow leaflets, m.p. 247°.

(c) *Oxazole formation.*—Same procedure as in the case of the 1:2-diacetyl-3-aminoalizarin was adopted. The product formed light grey shining needles, not melting below 310°, yield 71%. (Found: C, 75.19; H, 3.78; N, 3.30. $C_{21}H_{11}O_3N$ requires C, 75.51; H, 3.37; N, 3.14 per cent).

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